

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

Rβg[^]-CLOSED SETS IN TOPOLOGICAL SPACES

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ABSTRACT

Firstly, we introduce the concept of rβg[^]-closed sets as a new type of g-closed sets. Then, we investigate some properties of them. We obtain that it is stronger than both rg-closed and rβg-closed. Then, we give a diagram. Besides, we define a complement of it and give a characterization and some properties similarly.

Keywords: g-closed sets, rg-closed sets, wsr-sets, rβg-closed sets, rβg[^]-closed sets.

1. INTRODUCTION

Of course, open sets and so closed sets are the basic notions of point-set topology. Levine[5] introduced the notion of generalized closed sets as a generalization of closed sets. Then, Dunham[2] defined the notion of the closure operator cl^* and investigated properties of them. Besides, he introduced a topology τ^* and related interior operator int^* . Several authors studied on g-closed sets such as [3],[4],[6],[7]. In fact, the purpose of this study is to introduce a new type of g-closed sets namely rβg[^]-closed sets. Topology is a special subcollection of $P(Z)$ such that $P(Z)$ is power set of Z . We use the symbol (Z, τ) for a topological space. For a subset X of Z , the closure of T and the interior of T are denoted by $cl(T)$ and $int(T)$, respectively in a space (Z, τ) . It is known that a subset T is said to be regular open (resp. regular closed) [9] if $T = int(cl(T))$ (resp. $T = cl(int(T))$).

2. PRELIMINARIES

In this section we recall necessary definitions.

Definition 2.1. A subset X of a topological space (Z, τ) is called

- (1) β -open[1] if $cl(int(cl(X)))$,
- (2) β -closed[1] if $(Z-X)$ is β -open,
- (3) β -regular[6] or weak semi-regular set[3](briefly, wsr-set) if X is both β -open and β -closed.

Definition 2.2. A subset X of a topological space (Z, τ) is called

- (1) generalized closed (briefly, g-closed)[5] if $cl(X) \subseteq U$ whenever $X \subseteq U$ and U is open in Z ,
- (2) regular generalized closed (briefly, rg-closed)[7] if $cl(X) \subseteq U$ whenever $X \subseteq U$ and U is regular open in Z ,
- (3) rβg-closed [4] if $cl(X) \subseteq U$ whenever $X \subseteq U$ and U is wsr in Z ,
- (4) generalized open (briefly, g-open)[5] if $(Z-X)$ is g-closed.

$WSR(Z)$, $GC(Z)$ and $GO(Z)$ denotes the collection of all wsr-sets, g-closed sets and g-open sets in (Z, τ) , respectively.

Lemma 2.3. If $X \in WSR(Z)$, then $(Z-X) \in WSR(Z)$ [3].

Lemma 2.4. In any topological space (Z, τ) , the following properties are hold:

- (1) Every closed set is g-closed[6].
- (2) Every g-closed set is rg-closed[7].
- (3) Every closed set is rβg[^]-closed[4].

Corollary 2.5. Every closed set is rg-closed.

Definition 2.6. For a subset X of a topological space (Z, τ) , the generalized closure operator $cl^*[2]$ is defined by the intersection of all g-closed sets containing X , i.e., $cl^*(X) = \bigcap \{F \subseteq Z : X \subseteq F \in GC(Z)\}$.

Lemma 2.6. cl^* is a Kuratowski Closure Operator. [2]

The next definition is given in [2].

Definition 2.7. Let a subset X of a topological space (Z, τ) .

- (1) $\tau^* = \{X : cl^*(Z-X) = Z-X\}$ is a topology on Z .
- (2) $int^*(X) = \bigcup \{V \subseteq Z : V \in GO(Z), V \subseteq X\}$
- (3) If $X \in \tau^*$, then X is called τ^* -open, i.e., $int^*(X) = X$.
- (4) If $(Z-X) \in \tau^*$, then X is called τ^* -closed, i.e., $cl^*(X) = X$.

Lemma 2.8. For the subset X of a topological space (Z, τ) , then the next relations are hold:

- (1) $cl^*(X) \subseteq cl(X)$,
- (2) $\tau \subseteq \tau^*$.

3. Rβg[^]-CLOSED SETS AND Rβg[^]-OPEN SETS

In this section, we define a type of generalized closed sets using wsr-set and cl^* operator and investigate some properties of it. Besides we introduce complement of it as a new type of g-open sets.

Definiton 3.1. A subset X of a topological space (Z, τ) is called

- (1) rβg[^]-closed if $cl^*(X) \subseteq U$ whenever $X \subseteq U$ and U is wsr-set in Z ,
- (2) rβg[^]-open set if $(Z-X)$ is a rβg[^]-closed.

Theorem 3.2. In any space (Z, τ) , every closed set is rβg[^]-closed.

Proof. Let $X \subseteq Z$ is closed set and $X \subseteq U \in WSR(Z)$. Then, $cl(X) = X \subseteq U$. From Lemma 2.1, we have $cl^*(X) \subseteq cl(X) \subseteq U$ and hence $cl^*(X) \subseteq U$. Therefore, $cl^*(X) \subseteq U$ whenever $X \subseteq U$ and U is wsr in Z . This shows that X is rβg[^]-closed.

Corollary 3.3. rβg[^]-closedness is a generalization of closedness.

Remark 3.4. The converse of the above theorem need not be true as seen from the next example.

Example 3.5. Consider the topological space $Z = \{a, b, c, d\}$ with topology $\tau = \{\emptyset, Z, \{a\}, \{b, d\}, \{a, b, d\}\}$. Then, $X = \{b, c\}$ is a $r\beta g^\wedge$ -closed but not closed.

Theorem 3.6. In any space (Z, τ) , every $r\beta g^\wedge$ -closed set is $r\beta g^\wedge$ -closed.

Proof. The proof is obvious from Lemma 2.8(1).

Remark 3.7. The converse of the above theorem need not be true as seen from the next example.

Example 3.8. Let (Z, τ) be a topological space and $X = \{b, c\}$ be a subset of Z as in Example 3.5. Then, $X = \{b, c\}$ is a $r\beta g^\wedge$ -closed but not $r\beta g$ -closed.

Proposition 3.9. In any space (Z, τ) , every regular open set is wsr -set.

Proof. Let X is a regular open set in Z . Then, $X = \text{int}(\text{cl}(X))$ and we have $\text{cl}(X) = \text{cl}(\text{int}(\text{cl}(X)))$ by taking closure. Hence $X \subseteq \text{cl}(\text{int}(\text{cl}(X)))$ and this shows that X is β -open set. On the other hand, since X is regular open set it is open. Then, we have $X = \text{int}(X)$. By taking closure and interior respectively, $\text{cl}(X) = \text{cl}(\text{int}(X))$ and $X = \text{int}(\text{cl}(X)) = \text{int}(\text{cl}(\text{int}(\text{cl}(X))))$. Hence $\text{int}(\text{cl}(\text{int}(\text{cl}(X)))) \subseteq X$ and this shows that X is β -closed.

Eventually, X is wsr -set from Definition 2.1(3).

Theorem 3.10. In any space (Z, τ) , every rg -closed set is $r\beta g^\wedge$ -closed.

Proof. This proof is obtained by using Definition 2.2(2), Lemma 2.8, Definition 3.1 and Proposition 3.9.

Remark 3.11. The converse of the above theorem need not be true as seen from the next example.

Example 3.12. Let (Z, τ) be a topological space and $X = \{b, c\}$ be a subset of Z as in Example 3.5. Then, $X = \{b, c\}$ is a $r\beta g^\wedge$ -closed but not rg -closed.

Remark 3.13. We have the next diagram using Corollary 2.5, Theorem 3.2, Theorem 3.6 and Theorem 3.10.

One can the following fact using above diagram with Lemma 2.4(1) and Lemma 2.4(2).

Corollary 3.14. $r\beta g^\wedge$ -closedness is a new generalization of g -closedness.

Now, we give a property of $r\beta g^\wedge$ -closed sets.

Theorem 3.15. Let (Z, τ) be a topological space and $X \subseteq Z$. If X is $r\beta g^\wedge$ -closed, then $(\text{cl}^*(X) - X)$ contains no non-empty wsr -set.

Proof. Let $U \in WSR(Z)$ such that $U \subseteq (\text{cl}^*(X) - X)$. Then, $U \subseteq (Z - X)$ and so $X \subseteq (Z - U)$. Using X is $r\beta g^\wedge$ -closed and $(X - U)$ is wsr -set, $\text{cl}^*(X) \subseteq (X - U)$ and $U \subseteq (Z - \text{cl}^*(X))$. So, $U \subseteq [\text{cl}^*(X) \cap (Z - \text{cl}^*(X))] = \emptyset$. Therefore, U is empty.

Theorem 3.16. Let (Z, τ) be a topological space. If $X \subseteq Z$ is a $r\beta g^\wedge$ -closed set and $X \subseteq Y \subseteq \text{cl}^*(X)$, then $Y \subseteq Z$ is a $r\beta g^\wedge$ -closed.

Proof. Let X be a $r\beta g^\wedge$ -closed set such that $X \subseteq Y \subseteq \text{cl}^*(X)$. Let U be a wsr - set of Z such that $Y \subseteq U$. Since X is a $r\beta g^\wedge$ -closed, we have $\text{cl}^*(X) \subseteq U$. According to Lemma 2.6 since cl^* is a Kuratowski Closure Operator, we obtain that $\text{cl}^*(X) \subseteq \text{cl}^*(Y) \subseteq \text{cl}^*(\text{cl}^*(X)) = \text{cl}^*(X) \subseteq U$ and hence

$\text{cl}^*(Y) \subseteq U$. So, $U \subseteq Z$ is a wsr -set and $Y \subseteq Z$ is a $r\beta g^\wedge$ -closed.

Corollary 3.17. Let (Z, τ) be a topological space. If $X \subseteq Z$ is a $r\beta g^\wedge$ -open set and $\text{int}^*(X) \subseteq Y \subseteq X$, then $Y \subseteq Z$ is a $r\beta g^\wedge$ -open.

Proof. This proof is obtained from Theorem 3.16 and Definition 3.1.

Theorem 3.18. Let X be a subset of a topological space (Z, τ) . X is $r\beta g^\wedge$ -open set if and only if $U \subseteq \text{int}^*(X)$ whenever $U \subseteq X$ for any wsr -set U in Z .

Proof. Necessity: Let X is $r\beta g^\wedge$ -open set and $U \in WSR(Z)$, where $U \subseteq X$. Then, $(Z - X)$ is a $r\beta g^\wedge$ -closed and $(Z - X) \subseteq (Z - U)$. From Lemma 2.4, $(Z - U)$ is a wsr -set in Z and hence $\text{cl}^*(Z - X) = (Z - \text{int}^*(X)) \subseteq (Z - U)$. So, it is clear that $U \subseteq \text{int}^*(X)$.

Sufficiency: Let $U \subseteq \text{int}^*(X)$ whenever $U \subseteq X$ and $U \in WSR(Z)$. Then, $(Z - \text{int}^*(X)) = \text{cl}^*(Z - X) \subseteq (Z - U)$ whenever $(Z - X) \subseteq (Z - U) \in WSR(Z)$ from Lemma 2.4.. Hence, $(Z - X)$ is $r\beta g^\wedge$ -closed set and consequently X is $r\beta g^\wedge$ -open.

Theorem 3.19. If X and Y are $r\beta g^\wedge$ -open sets, then $(X \cap Y)$ is $r\beta g^\wedge$ -open.

Proof. Let $U \subseteq (X \cap Y)$ and U be a wsr set in Z . Since X and Y are $r\beta g^\wedge$ -open sets, we obtain that $U \subseteq \text{int}^*(X)$ and $U \subseteq \text{int}^*(Y)$. Besides, according to Definition 2.7(2) and Theorem 3.18, $(X \cap Y)$ is $r\beta g^\wedge$ -open.

Corollary 3.20. If F and K are $r\beta g^\wedge$ -closed sets, then $(F \cup K)$ is $r\beta g^\wedge$ -closed.

Proof. The proof is obtained by Definition 3.1 and Theorem 3.19.

We have the next fact as conclusion of Corollary 3.20.

Remark 3.21. $R\beta GC(Z)$ is closed under finite union.

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4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The notion of generalized closed sets is an important subject on topological spaces. So, we have devoted this article to investigating a new generalization of closed sets which name is $r\beta g^\wedge$ -closed. We give some properties of these sets. We introduce the notion of $r\beta g^\wedge$ -open set as complement of $r\beta g^\wedge$ -closed set and obtain some properties of them. Our future plan will focus on separation axioms of $r\beta g^\wedge$ -open sets and study on continuity using what we can get.

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